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TRANSFER OF GAME DEVELOPMENT KNOWLEDGE INTO THE DESIGN OF A MIXED REALITY GAME FOR ENGINEERING EDUCATION

A. Richert¹

TH Cologne University of Applied Sciences
Cologne, Germany

M. Schiffmann

TH Cologne University of Applied Sciences
Cologne, Germany

D. Wildemann

TH Cologne University of Applied Sciences
Cologne, Germany

M.A. Pauli

TH Cologne University of Applied Sciences
Cologne, Germany

C. Dick

TH Cologne University of Applied Sciences
Cologne, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Numbers of engineering students have continuously increased in recent decades. Didactic discourses in engineering education are strongly focused on competence-oriented, project- and experience-based learning. Due to the limited practical experience of first-year students, there are different levels of previous knowledge and a low student motivation for contents like management competencies and methodical skills. A game-based approach was chosen to teach those topics to first semester students. But how to develop an educating game for large student numbers which ensures the achievement of the learning outcomes and conveys the missing practical experiences while having fun with the gameplay mechanics? Therefore the game "FutureING" was designed in an interdisciplinary team of engineers, game developers and communication scientists. The Mixed Reality Game combines augmented and virtual reality, presence and e-learning modules. Management, methodical and technical

¹ Corresponding Author

A.Richert

anja.richert@th-koeln.de

competencies are linked and implemented in practical project work. The game conception and design considers learnings from the interactive entertainment industry in order to ensure a motivating game play and a high educational value at the same time. The paper focusses on the transfer of gaming knowledge into the educational mixed reality game, shows the methods and design of the first playtests and gives an outlook on the game implementation in the engineering curriculum.

1 INTRODUCTION

Soft and methodic skills are an essential part of the engineering curriculum as the trend to competence-oriented, project- and experience-based learning in higher education initially demands for those skills. At large universities of applied sciences in Germany e.g. each winter semester cohorts of 850 engineering students from five different engineering disciplines are trained in the fields of communication, project management and team work (teaching module working techniques and project organisation) [1]. To tackle the challenge of teaching these skills in a practice-oriented and comprehensible way a game-based and experiential learning approach is utilized. The learning outcome of the Mixed Reality Game is as follows: The students are able to implement context-appropriate working techniques and project organisation forms. They are able to analyse project situations with the essential factors of project evaluation, remember different organisational moods and apply the appropriate learning, communication and work strategies as well as scientific approaches in order to be able to design and implement sustainable, complicated and complex specialist projects with scientific demands. To realise this, the mixed reality game “FutureING” consists of four modules which are connected to the learning outcome.

Fig. 1. Modules of FutureING

The “FutureING” e-learning module (TrainING Center) is used as knowledge resource for the students and provides video lecture for the topics like classic and agile project management, scientific working, team work and team development. Furthermore, technical specifications (e.g. industry 4.0 concepts) and information about problem-solving methodology are provided to empower the students to solve the tasks in an engineer kind of manner. To prove their gained knowledge online tests are provided.

The presence module is an integrative “lesson learned” part after each game module and is executed together with special trained coaches.

The students will be guided to reflect their behaviour and decision making. They will identify quality patterns e.g. in team work, communication and problem-solving methodology which are essential for the success of their team.

The overall concept of the game entails the students working together in consulting engineer teams which work on different tasks. The teams will get two main tasks: The first one is to create and optimize a new shop floor for a robotics company (AR module) with industry 4.0 technologies. In the second task the new shop floor is in operation and shows that the industry 4.0 production has to be optimized in some areas of the production chain (VR module). Withing FutureING the students apply management, methodical and technical knowledge in various situations and settings e.g. planning the production hall with a simulation. They become familiar with modern automation technologies, work on the state-of-the-art and achieve "budgets" for their projects to reach the next level. With the game-based learning approach of FutureING the students will be motivated to train and experience the level of their skills. The following section shows an approach for the development of an educational game for large classes which ensures the achievement of the learning outcomes and conveys the missing practical experiences while having fun with the gameplay mechanics.

2 LINKING OF IMMERSION, REFLECTION AND GAME MECHANICS AS METHODOLOGIC BASIS OF EDUCATING MIXED REALITY GAMES

2.1 Immersion and Refection within FutureING

Mixed Reality Games are particularly suitable for experience-based, immersive and reflexive learning contexts, since the consequences of playing them give the players immediate feedback on their actions - an "actio et reactio" experience is conveyed [2]. Another advantage is that this game concept can be scaled for a large number of listeners. Immersion refers to the process of defrosting into another world and forgetting time and space in reality. The more you immerse into the other world with all your senses, the more intense and lasting the experience. Strong audiovisual impressions, a realistic and exciting plot and settings and identification figures that seem as real as possible are an important factor for immersive learning. Immersion thus supports intensive experience and a form of "being present" of its own, which provides a basis for reflective learning processes. The visual development plays an important role in defining the immersive setting and providing context to situate tasks. One aspect impacting the credibility of the project for the target group is in which way the game environment represents the real-world context and how it can be used to improve the learning experience for students. To enhance the acceptance of students the project is aimed at, the game modules display the actual working environment in the industry in a simplified, more accessible manner, while also showing futuristic influences of industry 4.0. Players can experience the 3D environment through animated assembly cells and driverless transport systems which ties together abstract planning methods and practical, visually represented results. All modules follow the general rule of

providing an approachable and understandable visual design, especially for the AR module it was important to focus on the construction kit-like aspect of the game and displaying this through clear, contextualized user interfaces and machine designs inspired by real manufacturers' products. This visual development approach ensures that students receive a realistic, credible view on modern working processes and gain insights into possible changes in the way collaborative robots influence regular procedures. In didactic discourses, reflexivity is regarded as an important meta-competence for enabling optimal learning processes [3] and is realised in presence sessions. While immersion and reflection are basic prerequisites to build and process learning experience of the MR game, the learning process and outcomes will be supported by game mechanics and empirical knowledge from the entertainment industry as the next methodological sections show.

2.2 The AR Module and Its Game Mechanics

To realize a scalable game, the decision for the setup of the AR Module began with an internal survey conducted among 307 engineering students implied that over a third of them are used to playing on mobile devices, while 305 of them stated, that they own a smartphone. Mobile-based AR promised to spark curiosity among students, due to its novelty. A tracker, would anchor the play space around a fixed point, a beneficial side effect in a communication focused multiplayer learning game. Within the AR game, students collaborate in teams of six to design a production chain, using assembly cells and automated guided vehicle systems. In order to meet contracts, each manufactured product needs to go through four steps of production. There are three different product sizes, and assembly cells are specialized in different sizes and production steps. Each contract specifies a budget and timeframe, as well as a production volume to be met. There are two roles in the AR module: Researching available machines, and arranging the machines. One player can purchase and place assembly cells and automated guided vehicles on the projected production floor. The other five players have access to a brochure, providing detailed information on the assembly cells and AGVs (Automated Guided Vehicle), unavailable to the first player.

Fig. 2. Screenshot AR Game

They can't however, purchase or place anything. Thus, communication and cooperation is needed. Once the players have set up their production chain, they can watch

the factory in motion, simulating the assembly of the necessary pieces. If they succeed to meet the production volume, they get a three-star rating based on their expenses. Three game design concepts of the AR module are discussed in detail, as they were adapted from traditional ludic video games for their usefulness in an educational game. These mechanics allow for experimentation in a safe environment, reflection on one's approach, project management, communication and team work.

Providing different amounts of information and agency to players, playing collaboratively is a common practice in ludic multiplayer games, necessitating team play and communication. A recent example of a game completely centred around this dynamic is "Keep Talking and Nobody Explodes" [4], in which players need to disarm procedurally generated bombs, providing one player with the ability to do so, but no information how, and the other player only with a bomb-defusal handbook [4]. In his 2016 Game Developers Conference talk, Keep Talking and Nobody Explodes designer Ben Kane describes how the game was specifically designed around player conversations and collaborative decision-making [5]. Providing different amounts of information and agency to players, playing collaboratively is a common practice in ludic multiplayer games, necessitating team play and communication. Applying this dynamic to an educational-game to incentivize team play and communication in a practice-based learning and teaching environment seems definitely promising. And first playtests show its success in requiring players to communicate and actively collaborate.

A second concept adapted from traditional games, particularly for learning outcome is that of a delayed simulation-based on initial player input. This two-phase gameplay division asks players to use their current understanding of a system, hypothesize on the results of their input, then execute. In the second phase, they get to observe the results of their input, without or with limited ability to alter their input.

These phases are then repeated, until players achieve their goal by refining their understanding of the underlying systems. A classic example of a ludic game that utilizes this simulation-based gameplay split is famously "Angry Birds". Players need to sling-shot birds into structures, in order to topple them, and eliminate the pigs inside. Players unknowingly need to make complex physical estimates about the slung birds' trajectories, their impact force at the structure, the structure's weak points, the different parts and materials of the structure any many more. They plan their shot, release the sling, and observe the ensuing destruction. Through short times between input and observation, players can quickly iterate, try out new approaches and methods and meanwhile improve their understanding of the game's physics system. [6]

This gameplay split seems to be a perfect match for use in an educational game, as it requires player observation and critical evaluation of one's previous attempts and allows players to form a model of a complex interacting system through play. This also means, however, that the quality of the learning outcome is largely dependent on the game system's accuracy and applicability to real systems.

An interesting challenge on this project was to abstract complex real-world systems into accessible gameplay for first semester students. Long interdependent real-world processes needed to be condensed, to still create a responsive game that reacts to player input, and affords a reasonable amount of iteration. The acquired player skills

still need to apply in the real world. Future exhaustive playtests on students will help in optimizing the game's mechanics for learning outcome.

The third game design concept used is a three-star rating at the end of each simulation, based on the quality of the players' approach. It is a common casual and puzzle game mechanic, for example, also used in "Angry Birds" [6]. It removes the binary of a typical win or lose statement, which makes the game more accessible and reinforces even early correct interactions with the game through positive feedback. Serving as a measurement achievement, it also allows players to reflect on their performance in comparison to their self-set goals, giving them a feeling of competence and increasing intrinsic motivation [7].

Iteration or second tries are encouraged, while the existence of a possible better solution is communicated through the star rating. Two of the six player types outlined by Nick Yee are likely to be additionally motivated through the use of this mechanic, players focusing on mastery of the game, and players focussed on achievement [8].

2.3 The VR Module and Its Game Mechanics

The second module is a multiplayer mixed reality VR game, asking players to service their previously created assembly line. Half of the students enter a VR production hall needing to detect and fix hardware - and software errors in a running factory. The other students have research and management tasks, played at a desktop PC or a desktop PC within VR or using an analog brochure.

The VR repair players, desktop players and brochure players will need to exchange information and tackle problems together to research, diagnose and fix the assembly cells. For example, the desktop players use their dynamic statistical information to point the repair players to potentially broken machines. The brochure players then can open the appropriate manual, as seen in "Keep Talking and Nobody Explodes" [4]. The repair players navigate the VR space (as seen in Fig. 3) and use diagnostic tools, for instance a voltmeter on the machines.

Fig.3. Screenshot Blockout VR Game

This way, players need to play through different production halls of increasing complexity, and are again given a star rating, dependent on the speed and quality of their problem solving.

Currently in the prototyping phase, a number of mechanics have already been laid out for the VR game, while more will yet emerge from the iterative development cycles. So far, the game takes advantage of the game design concepts of different amounts of information and star ratings outlined in the previous section. However, it embeds the two-phase simulation split within a continuously running game. Instead of player input and simulation being two long phases of play and observation, in the VR game, their cause and effect relationship becomes immediate. Action, observation and reflection stay at the core of this mechanic, but their frequency increases immensely. This altered mechanic tied to specific machines allows simultaneously occurring challenges, and lets players interact with them at the same time.

With a VR based teaching module, accessibility is an important concern, and has naturally influenced the game's fundamental design. Virtual Reality headsets are still causing motion sickness in a significant number of users, with a recent article on the Oculus Rift suggesting that under certain conditions over 50% of users could be affected, further implying a troubling gender-based difference in responses [9]. Thus, a Mixed-Reality approach with a non-VR-part is important when considering the accessibility of an educational VR game. The desktop roles can be played both in VR, and on a desktop PC, while the manuals can be opened or printed as PDF files anywhere.

3 CURRENT TESTING AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The AR module has been tested applying the framework for training evaluation as outlined by Kirkpatrick [10], and its adaptation for the purposes of testing serious games by K. Emmerich and M. Bockholt [11]. The first playtests with engineers ($n=8$) focussed on the first two levels of evaluation: The level of reaction, checking the quality of game mechanics and aesthetics, and the level of learning, whether users understand the dynamics at play within the presented system [11]. Initially, open questions and criteria were defined, allowing the creation of a testable play situation and a test protocol. Given the early stage of development, a qualitative approach to the test was preferable. In order to gather both subjective and objective data, a two-phase questionnaire was created. Players played unobstructed, and their questions, comments and specified interactions were recorded. Then, they were asked particular questions, probing their fundamental understanding of the prototype, its rules, and their understanding of the underlying system. Further, users were asked to name enjoyable and unenjoyable parts of the play-experience. The described procedure allowed recording data on how users approach the game, unveiled qualitative areas with room for improvement and tested if users understood and could explain the underlying system represented in the game. The playtest data suggest, that users manage to understand, and explain the underlying system correctly, are able to accurately describe strategies for progression, and start experimenting with their new understanding after roughly 15 minutes of play. After their second planning phase, all testers managed to reach at least a one-star rating, while only one group reached a three-star rating after their second try. Generally, they observed the simulation phase carefully and were able to adapt their strategy accordingly. The testers enjoyed the setting and presentation. The social factor and

draw of a multiplayer AR were, stronger than expected, with non-testers quickly crowding around the testers, wanting to join the discussion or get a view of the organized production floor.

However, so far, only the learnability of the game's system has been tested. Further research and experiments need to be made on how students will translate game-knowledge into real-world applications thereof. Enabling them to do so, will require the system in the game, and the necessary player actions, to accurately portray and relate to real-world applications. Moreover, it needs to be clearly stated, that the playtest did not cover a large enough sample size, or an authentic enough sample, as it was done on engineering graduate students, as opposed to first-semester undergraduate students. The game is continuously improving and balancing and presentation are going to be honed to accomplish maximal real-world learning outcome. For now, the combination of ludic game mechanics, augmented reality and mixed reality applications shows engaging learning, practise and teaching potential. The results from the first rounds of playtests were used to optimize the game's accessibility, communication aspects, and the communication of its rules. A more representative playtest with engineering students was prepared for the beginning of April, but was unable to be performed, due to Covid-19 related closures of public institutions. This larger scale playtest expanded on the described formula, and shifted the focus to the second and third layers of Kirkpatrick's evaluation model of changed behaviour, learning and changed behaviour [10]. After playing, testers would have been asked to reflect on their social behaviour, and to judge, whether or not they think they learned something about engineering specific working, improved their project management and their ability to work in teams. Currently, an online multiplayer mode is being developed to allow players to test and play the game remotely.

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

In this paper the modules of the mixed reality game "FutureING" are described as one approach to bring soft skills and methodical knowledge to large classes of engineering students. In terms of constructive alignment, the competencies are assigned to the various learning modules. For this purpose, the levels of the corresponding actions are currently operationalised in the game by measuring the students' actions in the game and analysing in which level the competence was acquired by the students. The next steps for AR game are additional playtests with students and studies on what extend the learning outcomes are achieved. A first prototype of the VR game's underlying systems such as networked multiplayer, movement and repair tools has been made, and the project is expected to enter production in June 2020. Once a first completely playable version is made, playtests evaluating its learning outcomes and optimization can be made. The TrainING Center with online videos, tests, technical libraries etc. is already developed as an instance of the Ilias learning platform and currently used in combination with presence classroom simulations. The TrainING Center will be integrated into the game environment as soon as AR and VR modules are ready. The presence module for reflection and lessons learnt is already deployed and tested since the previous semester.

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